

The Impact of Peer Influence on Entrepreneurial Intentions Among Library and Information Science Undergraduates in South-West Nigeria

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Abstract

Purpose of the study: This study investigated the impact of peer influence on the entrepreneurial intention of Library and Information Science undergraduates in South-West, Nigeria.

Methodology: The research design adopted for the study was a descriptive survey design. A two-stage random sampling technique was used to draw the sample size. Data was collected from four hundred two (402) undergraduate students at three library and information science schools in South-West Nigeria through a questionnaire. Data analysis was done in an SPSS output format based on simple mean, standard deviation, frequency count and percentages to answer the research question.

Findings: The findings of the study revealed that the level of entrepreneurial intention is high ($\bar{x} = 50.51$; std. dev. = 6.297); undergraduates were positively influenced by their peers to engage in entrepreneurship; peer influence ($r = .110$; $p < 0.05$; $N = 352$) has a significant positive relationship with entrepreneurial intention.

Recommendations/Conclusion: This study highlights the importance of fostering positive peer networks to enhance entrepreneurial capacities among undergraduates and promote self-employment and innovation as viable career paths.

Paper Type: Empirical

Keywords: entrepreneurial intention, peer influence, Library and Information science undergraduates.

Introduction

Entrepreneurial development in Nigeria is critical, as universities produce numerous graduates annually, yet unemployment rates continue to rise. Despite their education, many African graduates struggle to find employment, as highlighted by Kigotho (2015). Entrepreneurship is seen as a potential solution, offering opportunities to address job shortages and practical skill gaps. Therefore, higher education institutions must play a key role in fostering young entrepreneurs to help curb unemployment. The increasing unemployment of Nigerian graduates, who are primarily trained for paid employment, has become a national crisis, with the gap between graduation and employment growing. To address this issue, entrepreneurship is seen as a viable alternative, and universities in Nigeria have integrated entrepreneurial education into their curricula.

Entrepreneurial intention can be measured based on several factors. Utami (2015) pointed out that entrepreneurial intention can be measured based on attitude, subjective norm and perceived behavioural control. Also, several authors such as Dinc and Budic (2016); Muhammad, Aliyu, and Ahmed (2015); Tentama, Jiamsari, Efiyulia, and Qodrati (2019) stated that attitude, subjective norm and perceived behavioural control are measures of entrepreneurial intention. In relation to library and information science undergraduates, they perceive that there is a decision on their intention to choose entrepreneurship that still requires the approval of individuals. Ponmani, Pretheeba, and Annapoorani

(2014) reported a moderate level of entrepreneurial intention among undergraduates in India to identify the level of entrepreneurial intention. It can be opined that that universities need to take decisive steps to disseminate entrepreneurial curricula and knowledge to all streams, most especially library and information science undergraduates. Based on the author's suggestion, it could be posited that undergraduates showed a relatively moderate level of attitude towards behaviour, and perceived behaviour control.

Peer influence is the pressure exerted by a peer group, encouraging individuals to change or achieve certain values or desires. It involves sharing knowledge and experiences and providing social or emotional support. According to Azua (2016), individuals, including library and information science undergraduates, are influenced by peers of similar age and educational background due to their need for social belonging and attachment. While they seek parental guidance at times, peer relationships offer intimacy, affection, and companionship, which play a vital role in their social and emotional well-being. Peer influence can be either positive or negative. Positive influence occurs when successful undergraduates inspire others to achieve similar success, while negative influence involves learning from others' misfortunes to avoid similar outcomes. Both types play a significant role in an undergraduate's development. However, peer pressure, especially negative, can lead to harmful decisions, including in entrepreneurial intentions. Tsang (2017) found that peer pressure among undergraduates in Hong Kong is often negative, influencing students' behaviour and decisions in undesirable ways. Understanding the effects of peer pressure is crucial for managing its impact on students' choices.

Supaat, Nizam, and Ahamat (2019) found a connection between peer influence and entrepreneurial intentions among Malaysian undergraduates, while Bhuyan and Pathak (2019) concluded that peer influence had no effect on entrepreneurial intentions in Uttarakhand, India. Despite some studies suggesting minimal peer influence on entrepreneurial behaviour, Usman and Yennita (2019) reported a strong peer influence among international students in Turkey, linking peer support to entrepreneurship. Undergraduates who feel supported by peers tend to have higher self-confidence and a greater interest in starting their own businesses. This study is therefore motivated by the need to explore the effect of peer influence on entrepreneurial intentions of library and information science undergraduates in South-west, Nigeria.

Statement of the problem

The assessment of the entrepreneurial intention of library and information science undergraduates is very vital due to the fact of continuous decline of the unemployment rate in Nigeria. Previous studies have shown that there is a moderate level of entrepreneurial intentions of undergraduates in universities; this perhaps may be due to the fact that their attitude and perceived behavioural control towards entrepreneurship is weak. One possible factor that could contribute to the entrepreneurial intention of undergraduates is peer influence. This could be done through emotional support, role modeling, shared values, and informational resources. Some of these studies have investigated peer pressure among undergraduates in social sciences, law school, and humanities. It is against this backdrop that this study set out to investigate the effect of peer pressure on entrepreneurial intentions of undergraduates in library schools in South-west, Nigeria.

Research questions

The following question was raised to guide the study;

1. What is the level of entrepreneurial intentions of library and information science undergraduates in South-West, Nigeria?
2. What are the peer influence factors of library and information science undergraduates in South-West, Nigeria?

Hypothesis

H₁ There is no significant relationship between peer influence and entrepreneurial intentions of library and information science undergraduates in South-West, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Entrepreneurial intention of undergraduates

Kibler (2013) defines entrepreneurship as a product of an entrepreneur's qualities and environmental context. Additionally, Fernández-Serrano and Romero (2013) submitted that entrepreneurship plays a crucial role in job creation and economic prosperity, which are the hallmarks of national development. Entrepreneurs are catalysts of change in a nation's economic sector. Furthermore, there have been several definitions attempted for entrepreneurial intention by research experts; notable among them is the definition given by Douglas and Fitzsimmons (2008), who described entrepreneurial intention as undergraduates' disposition towards the product of their actions and how they view their desire to take up business opportunities that come their way.

Entrepreneurial intention is measured by some indicators, which research experts have agreed to over time. These indicators include attitude, the subjective norm, and perceived behavioural control. Attitude refers to an individual's positive or negative evaluation of performing a specific behaviour. In behavioural models such as the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), attitude is a key determinant influencing an individual's intention to perform a behaviour. This evaluation is often shaped by personal beliefs about the outcomes of the behaviour and the perceived value of those outcomes (Ajzen, 1991). Attitudes are dynamic and can change with new experiences or information. Subjective norm represents the perceived social pressure to perform or not perform a specific behaviour. This construct reflects the influence of important others, such as peers, family, or societal expectations, on an individual's behavioural intentions (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). The subjective norm highlights the social dimension of decision-making, emphasizing the role of external expectations.

Perceived behavioural control refers to an individual's belief about their ability to perform a behaviour, considering the availability of resources and opportunities. PBC reflects the perceived ease or difficulty of carrying out a behaviour and is influenced by factors such as skills, time, and external constraints. In TPB, PBC directly impacts both behavioral intention and actual behavior, serving as a proxy for self-efficacy (Ajzen, 2002).

This assertion has been affirmed in a study carried out by Tkachev and Kolvereid (1999) cited in Chuah, Ting, Run and Cheah (2016) who revealed that in studying entrepreneurial intention among engineering and medical students in Russia, learned that all three elements of the theory of planned behaviour are predictors of entrepreneurial intention. A previous study on entrepreneurial intention suggested that entrepreneurial intention can be influenced or determined by how well entrepreneurship courses are taught among students by their instructors (Souitaris, Zerbinati and Al-Laham, 2007, cited in Chuah, Ting, Run and Cheah, 2016). With a similar study by Ojewunmi (2019) found that entrepreneurial intention among Nigerian undergraduates is moderate, with only 40% expressing interest in starting a business. This indicates that a minority of students are not interested in knowledge-based businesses and prefer white-collar jobs. This finding aligns with previous research by Keat, Selvarajah, and Meyer (2011), which found that university students are moderately inclined toward entrepreneurship.

Israr and Mazhar (2018) investigated a study on the entrepreneurial intention of University students in Italy. The findings of the study revealed that undergraduates in Italy have a higher potential of starting a business enterprise. The undergraduates who possess this potential are those in their early years of study and still have a young age. By implication, an undergraduate's age has a negative effect on the entrepreneurial intention of undergraduates. This study also revealed that undergraduates who have a young age and poor academic grades are more susceptible to starting a business enterprise of their own. Also, a study in Saudi Arabia by Alshagawi (2019) found that undergraduates have lower

entrepreneurial intentions, influenced by factors like lack of confidence, male-dominated economic environments, and stereotyping of entrepreneurial activity. The study suggests that universities should involve both business and non-business students in entrepreneurial education and training programs to help them learn the skills needed to start and manage their own businesses. High entrepreneurial intentions are not enough.

Pauceanu, Alpenidze, Edu and Zaharia (2018) researched the entrepreneurial intentions of undergraduates in universities in the United Arab Emirates. It was revealed that most of the students (74.5%), representing the majority of the undergraduates studied, have the intention of starting their own business enterprise. This result is in line with the study of Jabeen, Faisal and Katsioloudes (2017) who reported that undergraduates in the United Arab Emirates rank entrepreneurship as their most important choice of employment. However, this finding is in contrast to the findings of an earlier study released by Oxford Strategic Consulting in 2016, where it was reported that only a minority of undergraduates in the United Arab Emirates wanted to start their business. The implication of this is that there is a high level of entrepreneurship intentions among the undergraduates at the University of Botswana, which therefore translates to the fact that there will be an improvement in the economy of Botswana due to many undergraduates in the country taking up entrepreneurship.

Peer Influence of Undergraduates

Lashbrook (2000) highlights that undergraduates often influence each other positively, but peer influence can also be harmful, especially regarding education. Experts need to understand the complexities of peer influence to prevent negative impacts before they take hold. Peer influence can lead undergraduates to act inauthentically in order to gain acceptance. Additionally, peers, along with family and educational professionals, significantly shape how undergraduates live their daily lives. Oyeboade (2017) conducted a study on peer influence among undergraduates at the University of Ibadan. The findings revealed that most undergraduates were not significantly influenced by their peers and did not experience strong peer pressure. Many students found it difficult to comply with peer requests to perform certain actions. A norm test conducted in the study showed that undergraduates had a moderate level of peer influence overall.

Similarly, Spear and Kulbok (2001) noted that peer influence is not always negative, as peers can positively impact each other, encouraging behaviours like volunteering, academic success, and avoiding negative actions. Brechwald and Prinstein (2011) added that individuals are more likely to associate with peers who share similar attitudes, interests, and behaviours, such as music, politics, and fashion. Peers with strong influence often guide others toward actions that align with their preferences and values.

Peer influence and entrepreneurial intention of undergraduates

Falck, Heblich, and Luedemann (2012) conducted a study in Germany, revealing that undergraduates' entrepreneurial intentions are significantly shaped by their peer groups. Their research, based on the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) model, showed that peers involved in school businesses positively influenced their peers' entrepreneurial ambitions. The study further indicated that undergraduates with entrepreneurial intentions are more likely to plan to start businesses later in life. Similarly, Macstay (2008) found that undergraduates' entrepreneurial intentions can positively impact peer influence.

Joseph (2017) studied international undergraduates in Malaysia and found that peer influence, as a social norm, was a major factor in shaping entrepreneurial intentions. However, other studies showed mixed results. Ebewo, Shambare, and Rugimbana (2017) found peer influence to be an insignificant predictor of entrepreneurial intentions among Arts and Creative students in South Africa. In contrast, Odia and Odia (2013) found a strong and significant relationship between peer influence and entrepreneurial intentions among Nigerian undergraduates. On the other hand, Kabir, Haque, and

Sarwar (2017), studying undergraduates in Bangladesh, found no significant relationship between peer influence and entrepreneurial intentions, aligning with Kuratko, Morris, & Covin (2011), who also reported a lack of significant correlation between these factors. These findings suggest that the impact of peer influence on entrepreneurial intention may vary depending on the cultural and educational context.

Methodology

Research design

The descriptive survey research design was adopted. The population of this study consists of library and information science undergraduates in Southwest Nigeria. There are six universities in southwest Nigeria offering Library and information science: The University of Ibadan, Oyo State; Lead City University, Ibadan, Oyo State, Ajayi Crowther University, Oyo Town, Oyo State, Federal University Oye -Ekiti, Ekiti State, Adeleke University, Ede, Osun State, and Tai Solarin University, Ogun State. This study adopted a two-stage random sampling technique. With the use of this method, a simple random sampling technique was used to select 3 universities the University of Ibadan, Lead City University and Tai Solarin University of Education. The selected universities have a representation of a Federal, State and Private institution. In the second stage, a sampling fraction of 30% will be used to get a sample size of 402. The sample size is justified by Thomas (2003), who recommended a sample size of 500 as adequate for a population of 9,000, and Israel (1992), who presented two tables using both 30% to derive a sample size for population sizes between 500 and 100,000. The measuring instrument used for this study is the questionnaire. and entrepreneurial intention was adapted from Muhammad et al. (2015), while the peer influence scale was adapted from Oyeboade (2017). The data was collated and analysed using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentages, mean and standard deviation for the research questions.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the level of entrepreneurial intentions of library and information science undergraduates in South-West Nigeria?

Table 2: Level of entrepreneurial intentions of library and information science undergraduates in South-West, Nigeria

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	St.d
	Attitude						
1	I would rather be my own boss than have a secure job.	188 (53.4%)	128 (36.4%)	23 (6.5%)	13 (3.7%)	3.39	.7700
2	A career as an entrepreneur is attractive to me.	164 (46.6%)	164 (46.6%)	24 (6.8%)		3.40	.6140
3	If I had the opportunity and resources, I would like to start a firm.	209 (59.4%)	129 (36.6%)	10 (2.8%)	4 (1.1%)	3.54	.6118
4	Being an entrepreneur would entail great satisfaction for me.	188 (53.4%)	150 (42.6%)	13 (3.7%)	1 (0.3%)	3.49	.5846

5	I believe that if I were to start my business, I would certainly be successful.	196 (55.7%)	69 (19.6%)	46 (13.1%)	41 (11.6%)	3.19	1.0580
Subjective norm							
6.	My parents are positively oriented towards my future career as an entrepreneur.	220 (62.5%)	100 (28.4%)	31 (8.8%)	1 (0.3%)	3.53	.6659
7.	My friends see entrepreneurship as a logical choice for me.	80 (22.7%)	159 (45.2%)	100 (28.4%)	13 (3.7%)	2.87	.8024
8.	I believe that people who are important to me think that I should pursue a career as an entrepreneur.	90 (25.6%)	145 (41.2%)	80 (22.7%)	37 (10.5%)	2.81	.9343
9.	At my university, students are actively encouraged to pursue their own ideas.	138 (39.2%)	144 (40.9%)	32 (9.1%)	38 (10.8%)	3.09	.9540
10.	There is a well-functioning support infrastructure at my university that supports the start-up of new firms.	76 (21.6%)	78 (22.2%)	124 (35.2%)	74 (21%)	2.44	1.0499
Perceived behavioural control							
11.	To start a firm would be easy for me.	64 (18.2%)	234 (66.5%)	44 (12.5%)	10 (2.8%)	3.00	.6494
12.	To keep a firm working well is easy for me.	73 (20.7%)	166 (47.2%)	67 (19%)	46 (13.1%)	2.76	.9291
13.	I know how to develop an entrepreneurial project.	79 (22.4%)	176 (50%)	93 (26.4%)	4 (1.1%)	2.94	.7292
14.	If I tried to start a firm, I would have a high probability of succeeding.	140 (39.8%)	155 (44%)	53 (15.1%)	4 (1.1%)	3.22	.7382
15.	If I want, I could become self-employed after my studies.	186 (52.8%)	145 (41.2%)	18 (5.1%)	3 (0.9%)	3.46	.6348
16.	To start my own firm would probably be the best way for me to take advantage of my education.	166 (47.2%)	154 (43.8%)	25 (7.1%)	7 (2%)	3.36	.7024
Grand Mean						50.51	

Table 2 shows the results on the level of entrepreneurial intention of library and information science undergraduates in South West, Nigeria. The results showed that if they had the opportunity and resources, they would like to start a firm (\bar{x} = 3.54; std dev. = .6118); being an entrepreneur would entail great satisfaction for them (\bar{x} = 3.49; std dev. = .5846); their parents are positively oriented towards their

future career as an entrepreneur (\bar{x} =3.53; std dev. =.6659); in their University, they are actively encouraged to pursue their own ideas (\bar{x} =3.09; std dev. =.9540); if they want, they could become self-employed after their studies (\bar{x} =3.46; std dev. =.6348); to start their firm would probably be the best way for them to take advantage of their education (\bar{x} =3.36; std dev. =.7024). This implies that attitude, subjective norm and perceived behavioural control are able to adequately measure entrepreneurial intention as it reveals their willingness to start a business.

In order to establish the level of entrepreneurial intention possessed by library and information science undergraduates. A test of the norm was conducted; results showed that a scale between 1- 21.3 indicates a low entrepreneurial intention, 21.4 -42.6 indicates a moderate entrepreneurial intention and 42.7 – 64 indicates high entrepreneurial intention. The overall mean of the entrepreneurial intention of library and information science undergraduates is “50.51”. It can, therefore, be concluded that the level of entrepreneurial intention of library and information science undergraduates in South Nigeria is high. This implies that undergraduates are leaning towards creating or starting a business during or after their program in the library school. It is also clear from this that they have a strong intention to start a business which is related to their professional training.

Table 3: Test norm table of entrepreneurial intention level of library and information science undergraduates in South West, Nigeria.

Interval	Overall mean score	Remark
1 – 21.3		Low level
21.4 – 42.6		Average level
42.7 – 64	50.51	High level

Research Question 2: What are the peer influence factors of library and information science undergraduates in South-West, Nigeria?

Table 4: Peer influence factors of library and information science undergraduates.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	Std
	Positive influence						
1	I have friends who inspire me to be an entrepreneur.	157 (44.6%)	159 (45.2%)	19 (5.4%)	17 (4.8%)	3.30	.7795
2	I would like to be like my friends who have start-ups while in school.	198 (56.3%)	106 (30.1%)	26 (7.4%)	22 (6.3%)	3.36	.8696
3	I have friends who value entrepreneurship more.	125 (35.5%)	141 (40.1%)	63 (17.9%)	23 (6.5%)	3.05	.8920
4	I spend most of my time in school with friends discussing entrepreneurship.	57 (16.2%)	98 (27.8%)	147 (41.8%)	50 (14.2%)	2.46	.9267
5	I have friends who would want to start a firm.	94 (26.7%)	192 (54.5%)	34 (9.7%)	32 (9.1%)	2.99	.8539
	Negative influence						
6.	My peers could push me into doing just about anything.	61 (17.3%)	28 (8.0%)	139 (39.5%)	124 (35.2%)	2.07	1.0596
7.	My friends do not support my intention start a business.	25 (7.1%)	30 (8.5%)	121 (34.4%)	176 (50%)	1.73	.8929
8.	When at school, if a group of people discouraged me from starting a business, it would be hard to say no.	70 (19.9%)	88 (25%)	80 (22.7%)	114 (32.4%)	2.32	1.1261

9.	My peers make fun of students who try to do start a business.	26 (7.4%)	27 (7.7%)	118 (33.5%)	181 (51.4%)	1.71	.8970
10.	I care about and I am influenced by the opinion of my circle of close people not to engage in entrepreneurship.	20 (5.7%)	32 (9.1%)	166 (47.2%)	134 (38.1%)	1.82	.8184
	Weighted mean					2.48	

Table 4 shows the peer influence of library and information science undergraduates. The results showed that library and information science undergraduates have friends who inspire them to be entrepreneurs ($\bar{x}=3.30$; std dev. $=.7795$); they also responded that they would like to be like their friends who have start-ups while in school ($\bar{x}=3.36$; std dev. $=.8696$); they also have friends who value entrepreneurship more ($\bar{x}=3.05$; std dev. $=.8920$). On the other hand, it appears from the results from the table that peers making fun of students who try to start a business ($\bar{x}=1.71$; std dev. $=.8970$) does not affect their entrepreneurial intention. From the results, it can be inferred that library and information science undergraduates are positively influenced to start a business.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between peer influence and entrepreneurial intentions of library and information science undergraduates in South-West, Nigeria.

Table 5: Relationship between Peer influence and entrepreneurial intention of Library and Information Science undergraduates in South Nigeria.

Variables	N	Mean	St. Dev	Df	r	P	Sig
Entrepreneurial intention	352	50.51	6.297	351	.110	.038	S
Peer influence	352	24.81	4.690				

Table 5 shows the relationship between peer influence and entrepreneurial intention of library and information science undergraduates in South West, Nigeria. The table showed that peer influence ($r=.110$; $p < 0.05$; $N= 352$) has a significant positive relationship with the entrepreneurial intention of library and information science undergraduates in South West Nigeria. This implies that there is a positive linear association between peer influence and entrepreneurial intention of library and information science undergraduates in South West, Nigeria. This implies that the more peers influence themselves, the higher the likelihood of them developing entrepreneurial intention. Thus, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between peer influence and entrepreneurial intention of library and information science undergraduates in South West, Nigeria, is hereby rejected. A statistical figure of ($r=.110$; $p < 0.05$) shows that the P value is less than 0.05 degree of freedom set for the inferential statistics, therefore, the reason for rejecting the stated null hypothesis.

Discussion of findings

The finding of this study revealed that there is a high level of entrepreneurial intention among library and information science undergraduates in South West, Nigeria. The finding of this study is consistent with the findings of Ojewunmi (2019) in a survey of entrepreneurial intention of undergraduates in Nigeria who revealed a moderate level of entrepreneurial intention. It was further affirmed that as it affects students, starting a business has a way it can influence their intention to start a business. Among the benefits that come with entrepreneurship could be identified to include eradicating unemployment and the improvement in the standard of living of undergraduates. The finding of this study is also

consistent with the outcome of the study of Keat, Selvarajah and Meyer (2011) that university students were moderately inclined towards entrepreneurship intention.

Similarly, Dzomonda, Fatoki and Oni (2015) reported in their findings, which corroborates the outcome of the present study, that undergraduate university students at a South African University possessed a high level of entrepreneurial intentions albeit been aided by the fact that they are a business student in the University. This, however, does not take away the validity of the outcome of this study as it shows that undergraduates can also pursue courses in entrepreneurship in order to increase their willingness and intention to engage in a new start-up before or after the end of their academic pursuit in the tertiary institution. Israr and Mazhar (2018) also corroborated the findings of this study by reporting a high level of entrepreneurial intention among university students in Italy, thereby indicating that they have a higher potential for starting a business enterprise. Alshagawi (2019) was not left out among previous studies that further affirmed the outcome of the present study as it reported that in terms of educational major, business students reported higher intentions to become entrepreneurs.

In contrast to the findings of this study, it was revealed by Megibaru (2014), in a study conducted on undergraduates in Ethiopia, that young university graduating students are less likely to prefer to be entrepreneurs. The majority of the undergraduates did not plan to start their own knowledge-based business. This, therefore, brings to bear the fact that they possess a low level of entrepreneurial intention. Based on this submission, it can be inferred that the undergraduates of this institution would rather focus on their course of study and build a career path with it rather than get involved in business, which they may not have the time to put their commitment into.

The findings of this study revealed that the majority of library and information science undergraduates are influenced positively by their peers, especially in the aspect of entrepreneurial intention. In consonance with the findings of this study, Spear and Kulbok (2001), cited in Azua (2016), affirmed that the impact peers have on fellow individuals in the same peer group is not always for negative purposes, as the positivity gotten from it is evident. To support this assertion, undergraduates can impact their peers by engaging in positive behaviour such as volunteering in different capacities, academic performance, and influencing their peers to desist from any activities or behaviours that can put them in a bad image.

Also, Lashbrook (2000), cited in Korir and Kipkemboi (2014), supported the findings of this study by revealing that it is not surprising that undergraduates who belong to the same peer group influence themselves positively. It can then be inferred from these submissions that peers have a major influence on themselves when it comes to decision-making, especially on issues such as entrepreneurship. It should be said that if peers can influence one another negatively into carrying out acts such as drug addiction and improvement in their academic performance, then the submissions of the above authors appear to be valid. To validate this position further, Brechwald and Prinstein (2011) revealed that peers are likely to be involved with peers who belong to the same school of thought and have the same behavioural traits and attitudes, which is inclusive of a choice of music, political interests and choice of fashion. It can be inferred from the above statement that undergraduates who belong to the same school of thought when it comes to entrepreneurship are those who have the tendency to influence their peers to start a business.

In contrast to the findings of this study, a study by Oyeboade (2017) on the peer influence of undergraduates at the University of Ibadan further revealed that a majority of the undergraduates submitted that they did not feel peer pressure. It was also revealed that undergraduates find it difficult to oblige when their peers request them to carry out an act. In order to ascertain the level of peer influence on undergraduate students. It can be inferred from the above submission that not all adolescents or individuals put the basis of their decision-making on their peers or allow them to influence them in any form.

The findings of this study revealed that there is a significant relationship between peer influence and entrepreneurial intention of library and information science undergraduates in South West Nigeria. To

corroborate this finding, Falck, Hebllich and Luedemann (2012), in a study on undergraduates in Germany, reported that an undergraduate's peer group shapes an undergraduate's entrepreneurial intention. This, therefore, indicates a significant relationship between the two variables. Similarly, Macstay (2008) supported the findings of this study by reporting a positive and significant relationship between peer influence and the entrepreneurial intention of undergraduates. Albeit with the possibility of positively affecting peers in making the right decision to start a new business.

Joseph (2017) was also not left out as the study pointed out a crucial finding: peer influence was a major determinant of entrepreneurial intention among international undergraduate students in Malaysia. Odia and Odia (2013), in their study of undergraduates in Nigeria, found that the relationship between peer influence and entrepreneurial intention is significant and strong. In contrast, Ebewo, Shambare and Rugimbana (2017) found that peer influence was an insignificant predictor of Arts and Creative students' entrepreneurial intentions in South Africa. In further contrast to the findings of this study, Kabir, Haque and Sarwar (2017) reported in a study on undergraduates in Bangladesh that the relationship between peer influence and entrepreneurial intention is not significant. The results agreed with researchers such as and Kuratko, Morris, & Covin (2011), who also found no significant relationship between peer influence and entrepreneurial intention.

Conclusion

The study indicates that there is a high level of entrepreneurial intention among library and information science undergraduates in South-West Nigeria. This aligns with numerous studies across various contexts, affirming that entrepreneurial intention is a prevalent trait among university students when influenced by factors such as peer interaction and potential benefits like improved employability and living standards. Peer influence emerged as a critical factor, with positive reinforcement from peers significantly enhancing entrepreneurial intentions. This underscores the social dynamics at play in decision-making processes among undergraduates, particularly when aligned with shared goals and attitudes. Contrasts with other studies, such as those conducted in Ethiopia and South Africa, suggest that the level of entrepreneurial intention and the role of peer influence may vary by context, including cultural, educational, and economic factors. Similarly, while some studies found a significant relationship between peer influence and entrepreneurial intention, others reported no significant connection, indicating that the impact of peers might depend on the specific characteristics of the peer group and individuals. Ultimately, this study highlights the importance of fostering positive peer networks and providing institutional support to enhance entrepreneurial capacities among undergraduates, promoting self-employment and innovation as viable career paths.

Recommendation

University management should encourage various departments where different courses are studied to make provision for a course that is visible and practical in their curriculum. This will help sustain their momentum and their intention to start a business. In addition, entrepreneurship programs, training, and workshops should be organized by the university management from time to time to help sustain their high level of entrepreneurial intention. They should encourage awarding grants to deserving undergraduate entrepreneurs or intending ones, especially through business proposals. Also, undergraduates should not shy away from identifying with their peers. However, they must do so cautiously by associating themselves with peers, groups, and platforms that align with their intentions and school of thought so that they will not be influenced negatively at any point in time.

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